

EBFMC25-OP-70 · Investigation of Treatment's Impact on Quality of Life and Psychosocial Effects in Patients with Psoriasis

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The aim of this study was to evaluate the relationship between change in treatment and change in quality of life in people with psoriasis who applied to family medicine and dermatology outpatient clinics. **Materials and Methods:** 100 patients who applied to the Dermatology and Venereal Diseases Clinic of Giresun Training and Research Hospital were included in the study. Sociodemographic form, Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI), Dermatologic Life Quality Index (DLQI), Psoriasis Quality of Life Scale (PQLS) were applied to these patients.

Results: In our study, the posttest scores of the patients who received systemic conventional therapy in their subsequent treatment on the PASI, DLQI, PQLS scale and sub-dimensions of the PQLS scale decreased significantly compared to the pretest scores. The posttest scores of the patients who used biological agents in their subsequent treatment in terms of PASI, DLQI, PQLS scale and sub-dimensions of the PQLS scale decreased significantly compared to the pretest scores. Biological agent treatment method was more effective than systematic conventional treatment and PUVA treatment methods in terms of DLQI and PQLS.

Conclusion: In our study, when the effects of the methods used in the treatment of psoriasis on quality of life were evaluated, it was shown that biological agents were significantly more effective than other treatment methods. However, it should be taken into consideration that individual patient characteristics and treatment responses may vary.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Psoriasis, quality of life, topical treatment, systemic treatment, biological treatment, PUVA

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting the skin, characterized by periods of remission and relapse, and is mediated by the immune system. In this disease, lesions are typically distributed symmetrically and are defined by sharply demarcated, red inflammatory plaques. Psoriasis is a common chronic inflammatory disease with prevalence of 0.33%-0.6% in different races and affects around 125 million people worldwide. The age of onset follows a bimodal pattern, with peaks occurring between 30–39 and 60–69 years in men, whereas in women, these peaks tend to occur about a decade earlier. Psoriasis is a complex disease influenced by a variety of both external and internal factors. Genetic predisposition is viewed as a significant contributor, particularly among those who experience the condition's onset at a younger age (before 40 years).

Psoriasis is a persistent inflammatory skin disorder that leads to the formation of scaly, hardened, and reddish plaques on the skin's surface. The primary histological features of psoriasis include increased epidermal cell production, an expansion of blood vessels in the dermis, and an inflammatory infiltration of leukocytes, predominantly found within the dermal layer. Recognizing the biological nature of psoriasis, it is now classified as an autoimmune disease that has profound health implications extending well beyond the skin. Psoriasis is linked to a higher risk of various comorbidities, such as cardiovascular disease, psoriatic arthritis, mental health issues, and other immune-mediated conditions. Studies have demonstrated that only 25% of patients are satisfied with their treatment, while more than 50% find the treatment moderately sufficient, and 20% deem it insufficient. This study investigates the effectiveness of different treatment types and their impact on quality of life in individuals who have either not started treatment or have had their treatment regimen changed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards defined by the Institutional Research Committee and the 1964 Helsinki Declaration. Before the study, approval was received from the local ethics committee of the university (decision number and date: 01/28-03-2024). The research population consists of individuals diagnosed with psoriasis who applied to the Dermatology and Venereal Diseases Department of Giresun Training and Research Hospital between May 14, 2024, and August 1, 2024. In the study, a pre-test was administered to patients with psoriasis before the treatment change. Data were collected by applying a post-test at least one month after the treatment change. The pre-treatment and post-treatment questionnaires were conducted using a face-to-face interview technique. The sample size of the study is represented by 400 adult individuals who applied to the Dermatology and Venereal Diseases outpatient clinic and were diagnosed with psoriasis within a year. Using Epi Info™ (CDC), the required number of individuals was determined to be 70 with a 2% prevalence, 5% margin of error, and 99.9% confidence interval. In this study, data were collected from 100 individuals.

The data were analyzed using SPSS software version 27.0. Descriptive statistics are presented as counts and percentage values. The analyses included the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, paired samples t-test, and one-way ANOVA. These tests were used to assess the changes in patients' quality of life scores on the PASI, DLQI, and PQLS scales before and after treatment. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

When examining Table 1, it is found that the PASI difference scores vary statistically significantly according to the treatment method. According to the results of the Scheffe test, which was conducted to determine which treatment groups showed differences, the difference scores for topical treatment are lower compared to systemic conventional and biological agent treatments. Therefore, in terms of the effectiveness of the PASI scores, the topical treatment method is less effective than the systemic conventional and biological agent treatment methods. The DLQI difference scores also vary statistically significantly according to the treatment method. Based on the Scheffe test results, the difference scores for biological agent treatment are higher compared to systemic conventional and PUVA treatments. Accordingly, the biological agent treatment method is more effective in terms of the DLQI compared to the systemic conventional and PUVA treatment methods. The PQLS difference scores show statistically significant variation according to the treatment method as well. The Scheffe test results indicate that the difference scores for biological agent treatment are higher than those for systemic conventional and PUVA treatments. Thus, the biological agent treatment method is more effective in terms of the PQLS than the systemic conventional and PUVA treatment methods (Table 1).

Table 1

Results of One-Way ANOVA by Treatment Method

Scales	Treatment Method	n	Mean	Std. Dev.	F	p	Significant Difference
PASI Difference	Topical	3	-2,8000	1,24900	2,975	,035	Topical vs. Systemic Conventional Topical vs. Biological Agent
	Systemic	42	-7,2690	3,02110			
	Conventional	10	-6,9400	3,55878			
	PUVA	45	-8,3244	3,69847			
	Biological Agent	100	-7,5770	3,47403			
DLQI Difference	Topical	3	-4,3333	2,51661	8,956	,000	Biological Agent vs. Systemic Conventional Biological Agent vs. PUVA
	Systemic	42	-7,3095	4,59845			
	Conventional	10	-3,3000	1,88856			
	PUVA	45	-	5,50601			
	Biological Agent	100	10,8444	5,38816			
PQLS Difference	Topical	3	-5,0000	2,00000	9,080	,000	Biological Agent vs. Systemic Conventional Biological Agent vs. PUVA
	Systemic	42	-	6,78973			
	Conventional	10	11,5952	3,55278			
	PUVA	45	-5,2000	8,30012			
	Biological Agent	100	16,4889	8,08655			
	Total	100	-	12,9600			

DISCUSSION

Mabuchi et al., aimed to assess the quality of life in psoriasis patients in Japan using the Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI) and analyze the relationship between this index and the clinical severity of the disease. Among the 102 Japanese patients who participated in the study, no significant difference was found in terms of gender, PASI, and itch VAS scores. However, the average DLQI scores were significantly higher in women compared to men. In our study, there was no significant relationship between gender and quality of life scales. This discrepancy may be due to the research being conducted in different geographic regions and the influence of varying environmental factors.

In the study conducted by Norris et al., the impact of biological treatments on the DLQI (Dermatology Life Quality Index) in psoriasis patients and the differences in DLQI score changes between different biological therapies were examined. The results revealed that patients with moderate to severe chronic plaque psoriasis who were treated with biological therapies showed the largest decrease in DLQI scores compared to other treatments. Our research supports these findings.

In Gelfand et al.'s study, it was noted that quality of life was more significantly affected in women than in men. However, in our study, no significant relationship was found between gender and quality of life scales. In the study conducted by Solmaz et al., it was determined that approximately 32% of psoriasis patients had a family history of psoriasis and/or PsA. In our study, the presence of psoriasis in the family was found to be 40%, yielding a similar result.

A study conducted by Muştu Koryürek et al. (2015) reported that psoriasis significantly affects individuals' quality of life due to its chronic nature, accompanying comorbidities, intensive treatment requirements, and the negative perceptions it creates in society. No significant relationship was found between disease severity, gender, demographic and socioeconomic factors, and the DLQI score ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, in our study, no significant relationship was found between patients' sociodemographic characteristics and their quality of life scale scores.

Owczarek and Jaworski (2016) evaluated the effects of the chronic nature of psoriasis and skin changes on patients' psychological health, self-esteem, and body image. The findings indicated that the severity of psoriatic changes, the duration since the last relapse, and gender had the most significant impact on quality of life. The severity of psoriatic changes negatively affected patients' somatic, psychological, environmental, and social functions, while the duration since the last relapse had a negative impact on social functionality.

Weiss et al. (2002) aimed to evaluate the impact of psoriasis on health in comparison to other primary medical conditions using three different health-related quality of life scales. Among the patients, 82.9% reported frequently feeling the need to conceal their psoriasis, while 74.3% stated that their self-confidence was affected by the disease. The EQ-5D health utility score was found to be 13.0% lower than that of healthy individuals ($P < .001$), and the general health and social functioning scores on the SF-36 were 13.2% ($P < .005$) and 18.7% ($P < .005$) lower, respectively.

CONCLUSION

One-way ANOVA and Scheffe post-hoc tests conducted to evaluate the comparative effectiveness of treatment methods revealed that topical treatment was less effective compared to other treatment options, whereas biological agents were found to be the most effective treatment method. Independent samples t-tests indicated that the difference scores obtained from the PASI, DLQI, and PQLI scales did not vary by gender, age, or family history of psoriasis, demonstrating that treatment outcomes were independent of these demographic factors.

One of the limitations of our study is that it was conducted in only one city and one center, which may have negatively affected the sample size and diversity.

In the selection of treatment methods, it should be considered that biological agents provide significant benefits; however, individual patient characteristics and treatment responses may vary.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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